

Investments in Ragnarok

Comparisons and Conclusions from the study of Media, Business, and Government investments in End of the World myth, story, and preparation.

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ABSTRACT

End of the world investments violate typical biological evolutionary rules and the laws of energy. In order to avoid violating the law of conservation of energy, such behaviors must conform to stimulus-responses causality scenarios as are demonstrated in most scientific and evolutionary models. Policy makers and researchers should perform deeper and more thorough analysis and in comparison with Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMC) expected hypotheses in order to both verify the analyses and make recommendations for policy adjustments, such as drastic spending cuts for world-ending military spending or experimental geoengineering.

Key words: apocalypse - ticket sales - Star Wars - nuclear programs - entropy - EPEMC

Analysis

Investment in end of the world scenarios is a uniquely homo sapiens sapiens phenomenon. No other species have divested as many biological resources towards memory of or preparation for future encounters with the end of the world. This facet of human culture is worldwide. Investments tallied from multiple sources indicate a media and entertainment investment at about \$138.1 billion (1.7%), business related investment at about \$21.3 billion (0.3%), and Government spending on world-ending war apparati and defense measures are about \$7.99 **trillion** (98%). For perspective, even if the average family consumes \$50,000 of food a year this is about 159 million families. The current world population is 7.3 billion people. If the family size were an average of 3.5 (using data from 2017 for 68 countries) this is monetary investment of food for 556.5 billion people¹ or 76.2 years of current world population.²

This type of [wasteful] phenomenon demonstrates a much more important subconscious expenditure than typical meanings (ie, typical human conflict, passing interests, agricultural motivations or indeed any Darwinian survival mechanisms). The total expenditures on end of the world media and business are on similar orders of magnitude with the estimated damage costs of Hurricane Harvey (\$138 billion). However, the governmental costs of maintaining world-ending arsenals and defense systems (not including general military expenditures and drills, ie expressions of distrust of other homo sapiens sapiens), is on the order of magnitude of 26 years of record hurricane damage from 2017 (\$306 billion).

Based on the law of energy,³ it would be atypical to expect such an investment on paranoid stimuli, with almost no payoff⁴ and even major detractors and negative feedback loops. Based on the law of conservation such an expenditure, in a vacuum of biological stimulus *and* strong impetus to avoid unnecessary loss towards economic and caloric entropy, there must be a precipitating spark for this behavior, and it must have appeared since Biblical times, when we find a marked increased interest in worldwide end of the world myths: (1) Diluvian myth (2) cometary cataclysms (3) volcanic and geological chaos (4) celestial fears and (5) messianic legends and prophecies.

¹ Orders of magnitude preclude precision. The government investment numbers are based **only** on US government spending. Worldwide spending on nuclear programs is likely to exceed \$15 trillion since 1940. Ironically, almost none of it is for weapons pointed into space at asteroids and comets..

² Investments are usually short-term, but the Bible is estimated for 100 years, and USA Nuclear expenses are 78 years, annualized.

³ Energy is abundant but sparsely concentrated; all life is attempting to gather energy to create Order; but entropy is returning energy towards chaos by dispersing energy as sound and heat. Ergo: the primal life dictate is to gather and propagate energy, and avoid unnecessary losses.

⁴ The typical return on investment based on the Media and Business figures is ~6.5:1. However, government expenditures have no returns on investment. Most of the money will have been spent on payroll and subsidies to military contracts. That means that it is un-researchable with any precision.

Tables & Figures

Figure 1 - Investment Categories in Millions of dollars, note: log scale⁵

⁵ For Data sources, see Bibliography [14]

Figure 2 - Expenses by percentage

Figure 3 - Media Investments, by % (including Production costs)⁶

⁶ Previous statistics included Production in Business expenses

Impressions

The level of expenditures spent on end of the world media, business, and government spending are astronomical, as accords to an individual's scope or perspective. However, the EPEMC hypothesis provides that a cultural trauma (felt worldwide) has had a "red-ant stirring" effect upon mankind, and has led to an inordinate expenditure and desire to evolve atypical to the normal Darwinian curve.⁷ This is, again, far out of the norm. For example the shark, crocodile, snake, and cockroach have barely changed in form since the Mesozoic Extinction (ME) 65 million YBP. By several orders of magnitude (based on species extinction rates), that event was quite stronger than the Younger Dryas Event (YDE). However, only the YDE and the cataclysmic events that followed have given impetus to only one species (*homo sapiens sapiens*) to quickly evolve psychosomatically, socio-economically, and politico-religiously⁸, and to (contrary to human nature and common sense) invest heavily in technology and the scientific method for survival apparatus.

The impression is that of hurried (paranoid) expense, as one who is expecting another event or attack. Its analog would be the expenditure in fraud protection, anti-virus software, alarm systems, firearms, large dogs, and more in expectation of outside attack. However, in this case, the level of expense exceeds in order of magnitude by several times, all reasonableness. So instead of buying those things alone for oneself, buying them also for one's friends, family, extended family, co-workers, employees, colleagues, students, church-members, etc... until at every level a heightened expectation is ratcheted to extreme levels of hypersensitivity. It is no wonder, in this type of environment that investments in personal firearms, martial arts, and other self-protection mechanisms are so high, and that military spending exceeds the infrastructure budget.⁹

This paper makes no attempt to explain every facet of why these expenditures are high. There is a nostalgic and inherent entertainment value for end of the world movies which generates a type of earnest general interest (ie, the "popcorn" effect). A page-turning story or a hero's journey¹⁰ will always sell. However, media that specializes in themes of 'the gods', and the clash of forces greater than humanity, such as wars between opposing sides (much as seen in the Nordic myths or Mahabharata) - one of which is much more 'evil' than one's own side (eg: Harry Potter, and compare with the USA/USSR Cold War media coverage) - is inherently reflective of human historical and mythical experience. The dynamic of Othering is ubiquitous in humanity's martial experience, but not necessarily biologically indicative.¹¹

Given the economic value of the investment, not to mention the time investment,¹² it would be advisable to policy makers to study enhanced and specialized research upon this topic. However, it is necessary for researchers to re-consider the morphology of these myths in order to understand the grip of their power upon the Human psyche, and indeed, upon the common individual's media consumption experience and how they (and policy makers) think about interactions between: people, government, military, foreign nationalities, borders, and survival resources (which are shrinking on the surface, per capita and in total volume as measured per combustible and recyclable molecule).

⁷ Typical Darwinian curves would envision biological adaptations, but human growth in areas, such as tool use, far exceeds the rates seen with dolphins, primates, parrots, crows, etc...

⁸ "On the Origins of Religions", Sf. Careaga, 2018 [12]

⁹ 16.2% vs 13% [13]

¹⁰ The hero's journey, as described by Dr. Joseph Campbell (and typified in the original Star Wars trilogy), comes from Nordic, Egyptian, and Greek myth (such as Hercules/Heraclēs, Thor, and Osiris).

¹¹ Many forms of conflict exist with one, three, or more sides showing vested and complicated interests. The Warring States and Spring & Autumn period, as well as the Seven Kingdoms period, all demonstrate this.

¹² To say nothing of all the spinoff, bleed off, or black market side-effects of orthodox spending on such media and consumables (such as toys), There are also payroll and time resource considerations for journalism, pundits, critics, fanboys, fan-fiction, radio and podcast hours and advertising money, and musical cross-sampling

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¹³ Annualized and extended at a linear rate to 2018